

High silicon iron alloy from bauxite residue

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Abstract

Bauxite residue (BR) contains typically 20 to 50% iron oxide. A full valorisation of the BR requires that this iron is returned to the market. It is not difficult to recover this iron as pig iron, but the market price for pig iron is too low to make this economically viable. Iron alloys with high silicon content have higher value than pig iron, and BR contains between 5 and 15% silicon oxide. Therefore, it is attempted to produce iron alloys from BR with the maximum possible Si content, extracting as much silicon as possible from the BR and increasing the value of the metal. Bauxite residue sourced from 3 different alumina refineries and one legacy site have been tested in both fluxed and unfluxed experiments, supported by thermodynamic modelling. A maximum silicon-level of 17 wt% in the metal alloy has been achieved in experiments with BR fluxed with quartz.

Introduction

Bauxite residue (BR) represents a potential environmental issue, since the BR is strongly alkaline, and a potential land use issue, as land availability is becoming limited in many regions. Moreover, it is an issue of resource inefficiency, since the BR contains many potentially useful materials, among them the oxides of iron and silicon. The iron oxide content of BR is typically 20-50%. From the perspective of waste utilisation, it is an attractive proposition to recover this material as iron, and this has been the focus of many studies^{1,2}. However, the resulting pig iron is of low value, which is the main reason why these processes have never been implemented industrially. Ferrosilicon is more valuable than pig iron. If the silicon oxide in the BR could be recovered as silicon alloyed with the iron in a silicon rich alloy, this would mean a significant increase in the value of the product and a decrease of the amount of waste. This would have a meaningful positive impact on the business case and make realisation more likely.

Experimental details and methods

Four types of BR qualities were used, three from running bauxite refineries (BR A, C & D) and one from a legacy site (BR B). The compositions of the materials are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Material composition of the different bauxite residues. Roudned to 1 decimal, normalised, measured by XRF.

wt%	BR A	BR B*	BR C	BR D
CO ₂	2,1	18,9	2,4	3,4
Na ₂ O	5,3	3,0	3,0	9,0
MgO	0,1	1,2	0,3	0,1
Al ₂ O ₃	15,7	14,2	24,5	21,3
SiO ₂	8,6	13,6	7,6	12,5
CaO	5,9	17,4	9,2	4,5
TiO ₂	8,7	3,7	6,6	2,9
MnO	0,2	0,2	0,0	0,0
Fe ₂ O ₃	53,3	27,8	46,4	46,2
Initial moisture content (%)	23	22	26	36

* BR B is from a legacy site

The materials were charged into a graphite crucible and heated in an open induction furnace to the target temperature with a gradient of 20-25 °C/min, and kept at the target temperature for 1 hour. A slow cooldown was achieved by shutting off the furnace and leaving the crucible inside.

Three series of experiments were performed. A first, baseline series of experiments used BR and coke with no further fluxing at 1650 °C. The second series of experiments were fluxed with approximately 20 wt% quartz fines, while the third series of experiments were fluxed with this same amount of quartz fines but run at an increased temperature of 1750 °C. The coking levels were set based on complete stoichiometric reaction of all iron and silicon in the system according to $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + 3\text{C} = 2\text{Fe} + 3\text{CO}$ and $\text{SiO}_2 + 2\text{C} = \text{Si} + 2\text{CO}$, respectively. The third experimental series also charged some charcoal on top of the rest of the charge, in order to possibly capture SiO-gas. An overview of the experiments is shown in Table 2. The coke had a fixed carbon content of 87.7 wt%, the quartz was more than 99.2 wt% SiO₂. The metallic phase was analysed for silicon content after the experiments.

Thermodynamic modelling

The thermodynamic modelling was performed using FACTSage 7.3. The slags and oxide phases used data from the FACTOxide database, while FACTSteel was used for the liquid metal phases. The results of the thermodynamic modelling were used both in the planning of experiments and the interpretation of results.

Table 2. Overview of experiments.

	Exp. #	BR	BR-amount	T [°C]	Coke	Quartz	Charcoal on top
Series 1	1	BR A	92 %	1650	8 %	0 %	0 %
	2	BR B	94 %	1650	6 %	0 %	0 %
	3	BR C	93 %	1650	7 %	0 %	0 %
	4	BR D	93 %	1650	7 %	0 %	0 %
Series 2	5	BR A	74 %	1650	10 %	16 %	0 %
	6	BR B	76 %	1650	8 %	16 %	0 %
	7	BR C	74 %	1650	9 %	17 %	0 %
	8	BR D	74 %	1650	10 %	16 %	0 %
Series 3	9	BR A	68 %	1750	9 %	15 %	8 %
	10	BR B	69 %	1750	8 %	15 %	9 %
	11	BR C	67 %	1750	8 %	16 %	8 %
	12	BR D	68 %	1750	9 %	15 %	8 %

Results and Discussion

Silicon levels

After the experiment, the metal and slag phases sometimes separated easily, as shown in the cross section in Figure 1a and occasionally did not separate easily as shown in Fig. 1b. The level of separation between the metal and the slag seems to increase with the amount of Na which is present in the slag after the treatment. Material was lost during cutting, so a reliable quantitative evaluation of the amount of metal and slag produced is not possible.

The carbon content of the metal phase is between 5,3 and 5,7 wt%. The observed silicon-levels in the metallic phases are listed in Table 3 together with those predicted from thermodynamic calculations. In the unfluxed experiments, the maximum silicon level obtained was 1.8%, while in the second series of experiments with 20 wt% silica fines added, the silicon-content of the metal phase was from 2,7 wt% to 7,6 wt%. In equilibrium calculations where the carbon levels were set equal to the added coke, the metal in the unfluxed experiments was

predicted to be more or less free of silicon (<0,01%). This is because in the calculations C also reacts with TiO₂ and Na₂O, which limits the C available for Si-reduction. For calculations with different C-levels, the Si-levels increases with C-levels up to a maximum where it levels off. In Table 3, and elsewhere in the text, "low C" refers to calculations with carbon levels equal to that added as coke, while "high C" refers to the point at which the Si-levels in the metal is not limited by C. The "high C" calculations gave Si-levels in the metal from 7-12 wt% in the unfluxed experiments, and 21-24 wt% in the fluxed experiments.

Figure 1. Cross section of the graphite crucible showing the metal and slag phases from experiment No. 4(a) and No. 9(b).

Since the experiments were run in graphite crucibles, the real amount of C available for reduction was higher than the coke-additions/"low C"-case, and this could explain why the Si-levels are mostly intermediate between the "low C" and "high C" levels.

Table 3. Si- levels in the metal phases as measured by XRF, together with theoretical Si-levels as calculated by Factsage for the low and high carbon cases (wt%).

Exp. #	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Si, exp.	1,0	1,8	1,0	0,8	2,7	7,6	3,3	3,0	10,2	17,2	13,6	13,3
Si, low C	<0,001				0,09	13,4	1,1	2,4	0,2	13,6	1,4	2,6
Si, high C	7,8	8,3	7,3	12,0	21,6	24,0	22,1	24,0	24,2	28,1	24,9	24,7

The equilibrium calculations assume a steady/stagnant gas-phase of 1 atm. constant pressure. Calculations have also shown that the equilibrium Si-levels in the metal depends on the partial pressure of SiO in the gas phase. In reality, the gas will escape from the top of the charge, influencing the SiO-pressure and carrying some silicon away as SiO-gas. As a measure to limit the SiO-loss, the third series of experiments were run with charcoal charged on top of the BR-coke mixture. The idea was that SiO could react with C in the charcoal to form SiC and dissolve back into the metal phase. This also mimics the situation in a Si/FeSi-furnace, where SiO gas is captured by the raw material charge. These experiments with charcoal saw a significant increase in silicon-levels in the melt, up to 10-17,2

wt%, or increases by factors 2x-4x compared to the second series of experiments. Interestingly, the calculations did not show the same dramatic shift: In both the low-C case and the high-C case the predicted values were much closer between experiments 9-12 and 5-8 than the experimental values. This is an indication that the observed increase in Si-levels in experiments 9-12 are not primarily/solely a thermodynamic effect. Other effects could be: 1) that the application of charcoal does indeed limit the SiO-loss; 2) that increased temperature enhances reduction kinetics; 3) that increased temperature increases the thermodynamic driving force for reduction of SiO₂ and/or 4) that the increased temperature reduces the slag viscosity and improves mixing. Microprobe analyses of the slag has shown that no iron oxides are present in the slag. The XRF analysis of the slag shown the presence of iron. But this iron is present as metal droplets caught in the slag. Calculations on the effect of slag viscosity do not indicate that there is an obvious correlation between viscosity and Si-yield. While not conclusive, at this stage it is tentatively concluded that a reaction between charcoal and SiO-gas at least partially explains the observed increase in Si-levels.

Slag Composition

Table 4 shows the measured compositions of the slags of the 12 experiments. It is clear that the increased temperature during the experiments No. 9-12 compared to No. 5-8 have increased the Si content in the metal at the expense of the SiO₂ in the slag. The higher temperatures have also contributed to a decrease of the sodium content in the slag. The TiO₂ in the slag is not decreased when the temperature is increased. There is quite some iron metal caught in the slag phase. But since the distribution of these droplets is very inhomogeneous the Fe analysis from the slag are not reported here.

Microstructural Investigations

The microstructure of the metal from Experiment No. 12 is shown in Fig. 2. All metal samples have similar structures with graphite flakes and cubic Ti-carbides. Microstructure of the slag sample from experiment No. 11 is shown in Fig. 3. The structure of this sample is a mixture of an almost pure Al₂O₃ phase and a phase consisting of ca. 40 wt% Al₂O₃, 30 wt% SiO₂ and 30 wt% CaO.

Table 4. Composition of slags and Si content in the metal, wt%

wt%	Slag						Metal
No	SiO ₂	MgO	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	Na ₂ O	TiO ₂	Si
1	18,1	0,5	39,0	17,6	7,1	17,7	1,0
2	28,5	3,0	24,1	40,7	2,2	1,4	1,8
3	14,2	0,7	48,5	23,3	4,2	9,0	1,0
4	13,8	0,5	52,0	13,9	13,8	6,2	0,8
5	45,5	0,2	26,7	9,0	7,7	10,9	2,7
6	48,4	2,1	17,6	26,2	2,7	3,0	7,6
7	40,0	0,3	39,3	12,4	3,7	4,3	3,3
8	47,5	0,3	30,8	6,8	11,1	3,5	3,0
9	32,5	0,5	34,0	12,7	3,6	16,7	10,2
10	37,3	2,0	20,1	35,4	0,4	4,8	17,2
11	31,3	0,5	44,6	14,5	1,1	8,0	13,6
12	43,8	0,3	34,7	10,1	7,4	3,7	13,3

Figure 2. EPMA backscattered image showing graphite flakes and titanium carbides (cubic shapes) in the metal phase. Experiment No. 12.

Figure 3. EPMA backscattered image of the slag of experiment No. 11.

Conclusions

Based on the current investigation, we can state that:

- It is possible to produce a FeSi alloy with up to 17 wt% of Si from bauxite residue and silica fines.

- Silicon is partly lost due to SiO gas formation.
- Al₂O₃, MgO and CaO are exclusively concentrated in the slag phase.
- Titanium is divided between the slag as titanium-oxides and metal phase as titanium-carbides inclusions.
- Sodium content is reduced with between 30% to 60%.

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